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ELECTION SYSTEM BASED ON BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

There is no uncertainty that the chroma currency is very popular for the transaction information stored in the block of blocks. To initiate the importance of blocking, there is only one distributed ledger in which data is stored, since many of the centers in the blockchain network limit enough records for these records. This document proposes a decision-making framework based on innovation to create a secure, unjustifiable, accurate and transparent framework for voter privacy. In addition, it is voted and declared in this context that the race has a short period of time, since it is automatically registered in the table. This framework also gives society confidence in its legislation when applying this technique. In this framework, an administrator can add a candidate and a voter to the block. In different hands, a voter can log into the framework and then decide in favor of a candidate that the details of the vote should be stored in the block. In addition, each square in the blockchain innovation that relates to the previous square contains the hash of the previous square, and each square contains explicit data based on the square footage. The hub is connected by a peer network in this framework, with all the hubs in the block site network that have a complete duplicate block.

KEYWORDS

Blockchain, Election System, Proof of Work, Smart Contract, E-voting, Peer-to-peer Networks, Bitcoin, Ethereum, Democracy.

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Authentication and Verification of Social Networking Accounts Using Blockchain Technology

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ABSTRACT

Social networking pages authenticate by blockchain technology, through authenticating personal information and profile pages in the form of block and then distributing them with Blockchain to become a trusted reference point. To identified and verified social network accounts. This research proposed an effective and easy technical mechanism to authenticate the personal pages on social networks. Using this mechanism, anyone can authenticate any account on social networks, as well as increasing the possibility of making sure of the real individual behind social networking accounts. Moreover, this technique will show the fake accounts in order to reach a more confident and secure social network environment. Blockchain technique requires only a simple update to the characteristics of its platforms by developers, which is only a participatory mechanism between Blockchain and personal information. It is then combined with personal pages, to indicate that these pages contain the real personal information of the account holder, which is stored in an encrypted block that is difficult to modify, copy, or steal.

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